

Homo- and Heterometallic Clusters of Iron from Trihydrogenphosphine Complex, $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4\text{PH}_3$

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The $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4\text{PH}_3$ complex was brought into reaction with iron nonacarbonyl, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ and cobalt octacarbonyl, $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ in benzene medium and the iron cluster, $\text{Fe}_6(\text{CO})_{20}\text{P}_2$ as dark-red solid and the iron-cobalt cluster, $\text{FeCo}_3(\text{CO})_{12}\text{P}$ as dark-brown solid were respectively obtained. The products were characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight and infrared and mass spectral data.

Carbonyl metal trihydrogenphosphine complexes of chromium, molybdenum and tungsten, e.g. $\text{M}(\text{CO})_5\text{PH}_3$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cr}, \text{Mo}$ and W have been found to undergo dehydrogenation reaction with loss of all the three hydrogen atoms by cobalt octacarbonyl, $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ at room temperature¹ resulting to the formation of partially closed phosphorus bridged tetranuclear clusters, $\text{MCo}_3(\text{CO})_{14}\text{P}$ (1). The clusters consist of a tetrahedron involving three cobalt and one phosphorus atom and the heavy metal atom, M (Cr, Mo or W) being located outside the cluster framework at the top of the phosphorus atom.

$\text{M} = \text{Cr}, \text{Mo}$ or W
1

The reaction of the complex $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4\text{PH}_3$ (2) with iron nonacarbonyl, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ and cobalt octacarbonyl, $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ have been performed in order to see if these reactions at all provide any dehydrogenation at the phosphorus atom and also

whether complete dehydrogenation with the elimination of all the three hydrogen atoms takes place or the reaction leads to the formation of only partially dehydrogenated products.

Results and Discussion

The preparation of the starting complex 2 was made following the reported method² with some modifications as suited for the present purpose. In the reaction of 2 with $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ some reaction had appeared to have taken place but even after 20 h the extent of reaction was not appreciable as revealed by the ir spectra in the ν_{CO} region of the reaction mixture. The reaction temperature was then slowly raised and kept above 50° but below 60° , and the reaction was complete within 3–4 h. With $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ however, appreciable reaction was found to have taken place already at room temperature.

The clusters $\text{Fe}_6(\text{CO})_{20}\text{P}_2$ (3) and $\text{FeCo}_3(\text{CO})_{12}\text{P}$ (4) were obtained as dark-red and dark-brown solid respectively.

3

The ir spectra of compound **3** showed ν_{CO} bands in the expected range (2 200–2 000 cm^{-1}), suggestive of the presence of terminal CO groups. A band in the lower region of the spectrum (1 900–1 800 cm^{-1}) indicates the presence of CO

group bridged between two iron atoms in **3**. Compound **4** however showed ν_{CO} bands in the range expected for the presence of terminal CO groups only (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **3** AND **4**

Compd. no/ (M.p., °C)	Mol Wt. m/z (Calcd.)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)			ν_{CO} (cm^{-1})
		C	Fe	Co	
3 (236)	958 (957.2)	25.41	34.28	—	2 098, 2 082,
		(25.05)	(35.07)		2 048, 2 036
					2 020, 1 979
					1 864
4 (92)	600 (599.7)	24.27	10.14	30.24	2 115, 2 053
		(24.00)	(9.33)	(29.50)	2 018, 1 982
					1 954

The ir spectra of both **3** and **4** showed the presence of limited number of strong to medium but sharp bands, suggesting reasonably symmetric nature of the compounds. The ir spectral pattern also supports the presence of Fe_3 -triangle in the cluster framework with one bridging CO group^{3,4} in compound **3**. But for compound **4**, the ir spectral pattern was not typical for the presence of triangular Co_3 -framework¹. However, intermediate formation of compound **5** with a Co_3 -triangle and Fe being located outside the cluster framework, at the top of the phosphorus atom may be suggested.

Compound **5** then might have underwent elimination of one CO associated with the rupture of one Co–Co bond and formation of two additional Fe–Co bonds.

Mass spectra yielded the molecular weight of the compounds (Table 1). Successive loss of CO groups were observed for both **3** and **4**. Reasonable stability of the Fe–P–P–Fe and Fe–P bonds may be anticipated from the late splitting of the Fe_2P_2^+ ion and FeP^+ ion respectively. Results of elemental analysis agreed well with their formulations.

Experimental

All handlings of chemicals and the products were performed under nitrogen atmosphere. Iron nonacarbonyl⁵, cobalt octacarbonyl⁵ and trihydrogen phosphine⁶ were prepared by the known methods. Silica gel 60 was dried under vacuum at 160° before use.

Infrared spectra (cyclohexane) was measured on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra and elemental analysis of C were obtained from C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Iron and cobalt contents were determined by complexometric titration methods.

Preparation of 2 : $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ (1.82 g, 5 mmol) was suspended in 50 ml mixture of benzene- $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ (2 : 1) and stirred at room temperature with minimum exposure to external light. Freshly prepared and purified PH_3 gas was then introduced slowly into the reaction vessel. Fresh aliquots of PH_3 gas was introduced at intervals and the process was continued for 2 h. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 10 h in order to ensure completion of the reaction. The mixture

was then filtered and volume of the filtrate was reduced to ~10 ml by the removal of some benzene and $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ by slow vacuum evaporation. The solution was then introduced at the top of the silica gel chromatographic column which was pre-cooled by cold water circulation. Elution with benzene developed a yellow-brown fraction which was collected as the solution of compound 2.

Reaction of 2 with the metal carbonyls : Compound 2 in benzene solution was treated with excess of the metal carbonyls (molar ratio 1 : 3.5). With $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature under mild vacuum for ~ 20 h and then refluxed for another 3-4 h when the reaction mixture turned deep red-dish-brown. It was then cooled to room temperature and the volume was reduced to ~5 ml under high vacuum when volatile substances also got removed. It was chromatographed on a silica gel column. The fraction collected by elution with n-hexane-benzene (3 : 1), on removal of all the solvents under vacuum and recrystallisation from n-hexane-methylene chloride (3 : 1), yielded the cluster 3 as dark-red solid.

With $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature under mild vacuum for

~ 20 h when the reaction mixture turned deep brown. The volume was reduced to ~5 ml under high vacuum when volatile substances also got removed. It was chromatographed on a silica gel column. The fraction collected by eluting with n-hexane-benzene (5 : 1), on removal of all the solvents and recrystallisation from n-hexane-methylene chloride (3 : 1) gave cluster 4 as dark-brown solid.

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